

Some Chemical Ionization Mass Spectrometry Techniques for the Study of Natural Products¹

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Chemical ionization mass spectrometry (CI-MS) using ammonia as the reagent gas can exhibit the pseudomolecular ion of many complex natural products (e.g. alkaloids, steroids, glycosides, oligopeptides) without derivatization and with limited purification. Eluates from analytical thin layer chromatography spots can be submitted to a sequence of chemical reactions and monitored by CI-MS for obtaining structural information. Another powerful technique is negative chemical ionization mass spectrometry which may aid the sequence determination of oligopeptides and oligosaccharides without derivatization.

PLANTS of various types, medicinal or otherwise, continue to be favourite subjects of study by natural products' chemists. Amongst plant products alkaloids have received particular attention because of their physiological activity and their interesting chemistry. This communication describes some newer techniques for studying natural products.

The key aspect of chemical ionization (CI) is charge transfer to the compound under study to form positive or negative ions which are detected by a mass spectrometer². A reagent gas, for example CH₄, is introduced into the ion source of the mass spectrometer at a pressure of 1-3 torr and electrons of 500 v or higher energy are used to generate a 'plasma' (Scheme 1). An important constituent of the plasma from CH₄ is CH₃⁺ which behaves as a Bronsted acid that can provide protons to most molecules in a low energy process. As a result (M+H)⁺ ions, called pseudomolecular ions, are formed from the compound under study. Because of their low energy content these ions have little tendency to fragment and therefore produce almost exclusively high intensity peaks at m/e corresponding to M+1.

Scheme 1

Generation of plasma in CIMS

- (a) CH₄ + e → CH₃⁺, CH₂⁺, CH₂⁺, CH⁺, C⁺, H₃⁺, H⁺ + 2e
CH₃⁺ + CH₄ → CH₅⁺ + CH₃
CH₃⁺ + CH₄ → C, H₃⁺ + H₂
- (b) (CH₃)₃CH \xrightarrow{e} (CH₃)₃C⁺
- (c) H₂ + e → H₂⁺
- (d) NH₃ + CH₃⁺ → (NH₃)_nH⁺ (n = 1, 2, and 3)

Many reagent gases other than methane or isobutane have been studied³. Of special interest is ammonia which gives rise to NH₄⁺ ions. These ions can be captured by a molecule to produce (M+NH₄)⁺ ions detected as peaks at m/e M+18. The use of ammonia as a reagent gas increases greatly the chances

of observing the pseudomolecular ion and thus improves the sensitivity of the mass spectral method.

CIMS Studies on Sterols

We⁴ have found CI (NH₃) to be a valuable mass spectrometric technique for simplifying the study of a wide variety of biologically interesting molecules such as steroids, prostaglandins, fatty acids, penicillins, alkaloids, carbohydrates, etc. We describe here our findings on sterols.

Most plant materials contain sterols such as stigmasterol and sitosterol. A few micrograms of such sterols introduced into a CI mass spectrometer through a direct probe give intense pseudomolecular ions when ammonia is used as the reagent gas. Even steroids with several hydroxy or acetoxy (or other ester) groups produce (M+18)⁺ peaks, under electron impact mass spectrometry (EI-MS) such compounds usually produce only fragment ions. The presence or absence of a specific phytosterol can thus be determined by CI-MS in very small samples of specimens.

Resistance to fragmentation under CI-MS (NH₃) conditions is particularly valuable when studying natural products that occur as glycosides. In general, it is possible to record the spectrum of the intact glycoside (see Table 1) without silylation or derivatization of the free hydroxy groups.

The number of hydroxyl groups in a sterol can be determined by treating a less than mg size sample with Jones reagent and then submitting the crude reaction product to CI-MS examination. Information about unsaturation in the steroid can be obtained by RuO₄ oxidation. Treatment of a steroid with an acetone or carbon tetrachloride solution of RuO₄ for a few minutes converts isolated double bonds to carboxy groups. To determine the number of carboxy groups, the crude oxidation mixture can be stripped of solvent and a part used for obtaining a CI spectrum. Another part may be treated with CH₃N₂ and the CI mass spectrum

Scheme 2

CIMS Determination of the position of double bonds.

recorded again: each carboxy group would of course become a methyl ester and lead to an increase in molecular weight by 14 mass units. The sensitivity of CI mass spectrometry is such that scrapings from an analytical TLC spot may be adequate for performing a sequence of reactions. Since meaningful CI spectra can be recorded using samples containing low molecular weight impurities, there can be considerable saving in time and effort in following by CI-MS selected chemical reactions such as those outlined in Scheme 2 and the Experimental Section.

CI-MS Studies on Alkaloids

The CI-MS (NH_3) technique we have found to be very successful with alkaloids for observing pseudomolecular ions. Because of their basicity alkaloids produce $(M+H)^+$ ions instead of capturing NH_4^+ to generate $(M+NH_4)^+$ ions. A special advantage of using NH_3 as the reagent gas is that salts of alkaloids can be used directly—the spectrum corresponds to the protonated form of the free alkaloid base. Indole alkaloids including such multifunctional types as reserpine provide strong $(M+H)^+$ ions. Representative examples of our finding are shown in Table 1.

It is worth noting that yohimbine alkaloids give strong pseudomolecular ions even though the hydroxyl group β to the ester group is particularly prone to

dehydration. In the spectrum of hydrastine hydrochloride (Table 1), the strong fragment ion is due to the nitrogen containing moiety A rather than the nonbasic moiety B; obviously the nitrogen facilitates the retention of a positive charge on fragment A.

One disadvantage of CI-MS is that it does not ordinarily produce many fragment ions. The numerous fragment ions observed in EI-MS provide valuable structural information. In studying unknown natural products, say alkaloids, CI-MS presents a problem as far as structure determination is concerned. This can be partly rectified, however, by taking advantage of the finding that CI-MS ($Ar + H_2O$) produces many fragment ions⁶. By using a mixture of argon and ammonia as the reagent gas, we have observed extensive fragmentation of the same type as found in EI-MS spectra⁶.

Negative Chemical Ionization Mass Spectrometry

A new development of CI mass spectrometry has been the monitoring of negative ions resulting in striking increase in sensitivity⁷. In negative chemical ionization (NCI) the test molecule can capture a low energy electron to give M^- ions. Few fragment ions are usually seen in NCI spectra because of the very low energy content of the parent ion. This aspect of NCI spectra promises to be useful for studying oligopeptides and oligosaccharides.

Compound	TABLE 1 Structure	MW	Ions Observed
Yohimbine (hydrochloride)		354	355
Reserpine		354	
Aspidospermine			355 (M+H) ⁺ 340 (M-Me+H) ⁺ 313 (M-CH ₂ CO+H) ⁺ 283* M-CH ₂ CO -CH ₂ CH ₃ +H ⁺
Brucine (4H ₂ O)		394 (anhydrous)	395
Hydrastine hydrochloride		383 (free base)	384 (M+H) ⁺ 190 (A+H) ⁺
Asperuloside (hydrated) R = Acetate		414 (anhydrous)	432 (M + NH ₄) ⁺ +198 (sugar + NH ₄) ⁺ + other peaks

For observing the NCI spectra of oligopeptides it is not necessary to acylate the free amino group or esterify the carboxy group. Insertion of sub-milligram quantities of small peptides into the direct probe produces a strong $(M-H)^-$ ion. On the basis of a limited study in our laboratory, it appears that the few fragment ions seen in NCI spectra of peptides usually correspond to scission of peptide bonds. From Chart I it can be seen that sequence determination of oligopeptides from their NCI spectra appears feasible. Currently we⁹ are examining the possibility of sequence determination of oligosaccharides by NCI mass spectrometry.

Experimental

CI mass spectra were obtained by introducing sub-milligram quantities of samples into the direct probe of a "Biospect" instrument (manufactured by Scientific Research instruments, Baltimore, Md., U.S.A.) operated at 0.5 Kv ionization voltage under about 1 torr pressure of the reagent gas (methane or ammonia). For NCI spectra this instrument was modified by the manufacturer for providing a higher multiplier voltage (approximately 4 Kv) and reversed polarity of the detector.

Hydroxyl Group Determination

The free sterol fraction from human gall stone exhibited pseudomolecular ions at m/e 404 and 406 in $CI(NH_3)$ mass spectra. The major ion at m/e 404 $(386 + NH_4)^+$ correspond to cholesterol, a known component of gall stones. The m/e 406 ion was suspected to be a monohydroxy saturated sterol. Cholesterol, the major component of the sterol fraction was selectively converted by reaction with $AlBr_3$ to cholesteryl bromide and was separated easily from the saturated sterol on silica gel TLC plates.

The TLC spot corresponding to the more polar compound, namely the saturated sterol, was scraped off and the scrapings were eluted with CH_2Cl_2 . One part was treated with a few drops of Jones reagent. After a few minutes the unused oxidizing agent was destroyed with methanol and the reaction mixture was filtered and evaporated. The CI mass spectra of these two samples were compared. The pseudomolecular ion was at m/e 406 before oxidation and m/e 404 after oxidation showing thereby the presence of one hydroxyl group.

Double Bond Determination

The location of double bonds in sterols could be determined by oxidation with RuO_4 followed by $CI-MS(NH_3)$ examination. Sodium metaperiodate was dissolved in acetone: water (1:1) and RuO_2 was added to this solution with stirring until all black RuO_2 suspension was converted to a yellow RuO_4 solution. This solution was added to an acetone solution of the sterol under examination. After stirring for 10-15 min. the reaction mixture was concentrated and acidified with a few drops of 0.2 N HCl. This reaction mixture was extracted with ether and the ether solution was dried and stripped of solvent. A part of the residue was treated with an ether solution of CH_2N_2 . After a few minutes a stream of nitrogen was used to remove the unreacted CH_2N_2 and the solvent. The residues before and after treatment with diazomethane were submitted to direct probe $CI-MS(NH_3)$ examination.

When $\Delta^{5,9}$ -cholestadiene-3 β -ol was tested in the above fashion (Scheme 2), the major peak in the CI mass spectrum after RuO_4 oxidation was at m/e 412 (ion B).

After CH_2N_2 treatment these peaks changed to m/e 378 (ion A + CH_2) and m/e 440 (ion B + $2CH_2$). Similar oxidation of $\Delta^{4,9}$ -cholestadien-3-one (Scheme 2) gave a major peak at m/e 362 (ion C) which was shifted to m/e 376 (ion C + CH_2) after CH_2N_2 treatment. The double bond conjugated to the keto group did not undergo appreciable oxidation under the conditions used since no dicarboxylic acid was observed.

As expected, RuO_4 oxidizes the 3-OH group to the keto group too. Some of the reaction products therefore correspond to peaks of lower mass than those discussed above. It is interesting to note that these peaks from keto compounds usually are of lower intensity than the peaks from the corresponding hydroxy compounds.

References

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